

N-ACETYL-N-PHENYLHYDROXYLAMINE AS A SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC REAGENT FOR IRON

BY H. K. L. GUPTA AND N. C. SOGANI

N-Acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine furnishes purple, orange, and yellow coloured, water-soluble complexes with Fe(III) at pH below 1.2, between 1.8 and 3.5, and above 4.0 with absorbance peaks at 490, 470, and 425 m μ respectively. Purple-coloured complex is unstable. Orange complex is considered most suitable for detailed study as in its pH range there is less interference from foreign ions. The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 1 to 12 p.p.m. of iron at 470 m μ . Most of the commonly associated ions do not interfere. The reaction is not masked by tartrate, phosphate, and cyanide. The sensitivity of the colour reaction, determined in Nessler's cylinder, is 1 part of iron in 4,500,000 parts of solution and on spot plate is 0.2 γ of iron. The molecular extinction coefficient at 470 m μ and at pH 2.8 is 3.07×10^4 .

Shome (*Analyst*, 1950, 75, 27) has reported the use of *N*-benzoyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine as a gravimetric reagent for Fe(III), Al(III), and Ti(IV). Earlier (*Curr. Sci.*, 1944, 13, 257) he reported a list of compounds belonging to 'Cupferron' in which the nitroso group was replaced by R, where R = -CHO, -CO.Me, -CO.Ph, -CO.NH₂, -CO.NHPh, -CS.NH₂, -CS.NHPh, -CS.NH.CH₂CH₂. Feigl ("Chemistry of Specific, Selective, Sensitive Reactions", 1949, p. 166, Academic Press Inc., N.Y.) has also indicated the possibility of interesting results from these compounds. Preliminary investigation showed that *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine exhibited interesting colour reactions with Fe(III). Below pH 1.2 it shows purple colour, in pH range of 1.8 to 3.5 orange colour, and above pH 4.0, yellow colour. Purple-coloured complex is unstable. At higher pH there is a possibility of hydrolysis of diverse metal ions. Hence pH range between 1.8 and 3.5 is considered to be the most suitable for the spectrophotometric determination of iron either as such or in presence of almost all the commonly associated diverse ions. The development of colour is instantaneous and is stable for a reasonable period (2 hours at 34°). The reaction is not masked by tartrate, phosphate, and cyanide, but is masked by fluoride and oxalate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The Reagent.—Bamberger and Destraz (*Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1883) have reported the preparation of *N*-acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine by the action of acetic anhydride on phenylhydroxylamine. We have prepared it by the interaction of acetyl chloride and phenylhydroxylamine in benzene medium according to :

The reaction was carried out in presence of a little water and small lots of sodium bicarbonate were occasionally added to keep the medium slightly alkaline.

Phenylhydroxylamine (10.9 g.) was taken in a 250 c.c. r.b. flask and dissolved in 50 c.c. of benzene. Water (5 c.c.) and sodium bicarbonate (1 g.) were added to it. Acetyl chloride solution (10 g., dissolved in 10 c.c. of benzene) was gradually added from a burette. After each addition the mixture was vigorously shaken till effervescence had ceased. Water layer was kept alkaline to litmus by occasional addition of sodium bicarbonate. In all about 10 g. was required. Near the completion of the reaction, addition of acetyl chloride changed the colour of the reaction mixture from yellow to pink, which on further shaking changed to yellow. At this stage, before adding more acetyl chloride, a drop of reaction mixture was tested with Tollen's reagent. Negative test indicated completion of reaction. It took about 2½ hours for this operation. Benzene layer

was separated. The solvent was evaporated on a water bath. The product solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from hot water and also from benzene-petroleum ether mixture. In both the cases white shining needles were obtained, yield about 10 g., m.p. 66.5° (lit. m.p. 67-67.5°). (Found : N, 8.90. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9O_2N$: N, 9.27%).

N-Acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine is soluble in alcohol, benzene, ether, hot water, and NaOH solution, and it is very slightly soluble in petroleum ether. Its solubility in water at 33.5° is 4.7 g./100g. water. The compound is very stable in solid state, but its solution decomposes, if not stoppered properly.

Standard Fe(III) Solution.—AR-ferrous ammonium sulphate (3.92 g.) was oxidised in ammoniacal medium with H_2O_2 and was then dissolved in HCl (dil.) (Clowes and Coleman, "Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1947, p. 187). It was diluted to give 14 γ of Fe(III) per c.c.

10% HCl (v/v) and 5% sodium potassium tartrate (w/v) were used for adjusting the pH. 1.0% Reagent (w/v) solution in distilled water was used.

A Bausch and Lomb 'Spectronic-20' was used for measuring the absorption, using 1 cm cuvettes. pH measurements were made with a Beckman pH meter (model H-2). Visual colour comparisons were made with 50 c.c. Nessler's cylinders.

Spectral Characteristics of Iron Complexes.—Each of standard Fe(III) solutions (5 c.c.) containing 14 p.p.m. iron was taken in three 25 c.c. volumetric flasks and 1 c.c. of 5% sodium potassium tartrate solution was added in each flask. Varying amounts of 10% HCl and 1% NaOH solutions were added so that pH's of the final solutions were 1.0, 2.6, and 7.0. It was followed by 5 c.c. of the reagent solution and then the volume was made up to the mark. As reagent solution had no absorbance in the visible range, water was used as blank solution.

Fig. 1 shows the spectral characteristics of iron complexes at pH values 1.0, 2.6, and 7.0. At pH 1.0 the colour of the complex is purple with an absorbance peak at 490 $m\mu$ (curve 3); at pH 2.6, it is orange with an absorbance peak at 470 $m\mu$ (curve 2); and at pH 7.0 it is yellow with an absorbance peak at 425 $m\mu$ (curve 1). Thus formation of different complexes at different H^+ ion concentrations is clearly indicated (Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488).

FIG. 1

Effect of pH.—Several solutions were prepared, as described above, so that final pH of the solutions ranged between 0.5 and 11.0. Absorbance was measured both at 470 and 425 $m\mu$. At 470 $m\mu$ the constant absorbance is in the pH range 1.8 to 3.5 and again between pH 6.0 and 8.5; whereas at 425 $m\mu$ the constant maximum absorbance is in the pH range 6.0 to 8.5 (Fig. 2). In all subsequent work use of lower pH range and 470 $m\mu$ wave length was preferred as this condition increased the selectivity of the reagent and decreased the possibilities of hydrolysis of diverse ions.

FIG. 2
Effect of pH.

Effect of Time and Stability of Complex.—The full colour development of iron complex is almost instantaneous and is stable over 2 hours at 34°. The fading of the colour has been found to be due to the reducing effect of the reagent on ferric iron.

Effect of Temperature.—The colour of iron complex slightly decreases with an increase in temperature. There is no appreciable difference in absorbance taken at 25° and 35°. Hence maintaining the temperature within 30° ± 5° is considered desirable.

Reagent Concentration and Mole Ratio.—Solutions containing the same amount of iron and different quantities of the reagent were at pH 2.8 and absorbance was measured at 470 $m\mu$. Fig. 3

FIG. 3

shows the effect of increase of moles of the reagent per mole of iron on absorbance. There is a very gradual rise in absorbance, indicating that the iron complex is highly dissociated in dilute solution. Full development of colour is ensured at 1 to 100 ratio of iron to reagent.

Beer's Law.—Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range of 1 to 12 p.p.m. of iron between pH 1.8 and 3.5 and at 470 m μ . The molecular extinction coefficient has been found to be 3.071×10^3 .

Sensitivity of Reaction.—Sensitivity of the reaction was determined in Nessler's cylinders in the usual way and was found to be 1 of iron in 4,500,000 parts of solution. Spot plate sensitivity was found to be 0.2 γ of iron in 0.15 c.c. of the solution.

Procedure.—Ferric solution containing 25 to 300 γ of iron was taken into a 25 c.c. volumetric flask; 1 c.c. of 5% sodium potassium tartrate solution and a suitable quantity of 10% HCl were added to it so that pH of the final solution was between 1.8 and 3.5. 1% Reagent solution (10 c.c.) was added and the volume made up to the mark. Absorbance was measured at 470 m μ using water as blank.

Tolerance of Diverse Ions.—For studying the interference due to various diverse ions in the determination of iron, the procedure given above was followed. Ag⁺, Hg²⁺, Sn⁴⁺, Pb²⁺, Ce⁴⁺, ZrO₂²⁺, UO₂²⁺, alkali, and alkaline earth metals do not give any colour reaction and are not likely to interfere. Table I records the results. Only in cases of Cr²⁺, Co²⁺, Cu²⁺, Pd²⁺, and Pt⁴⁺ limiting concentrations have been determined. Au(III) is reduced by the reagent; V(IV) gives bluish violet colour and they interfere.

TABLE I

Fe³⁺ = 2.8 p.p.m.

Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion. (p.p.m.)	Ion.	Added as.	Conc. of ion. (p.p.m.)
Co ²⁺	Sulphate	120	Cr ²⁺	Sulphate	20
Ni ²⁺	"	320	Bi ³⁺	Nitrate	40
Cu ²⁺	"	200	Sb ³⁺	Sulphate	40
Mn ²⁺	Chloride	200	Ti ⁴⁺	"	50
Zn ²⁺	Sulphate	200	Pt ⁴⁺	Chloride	12
Cd ²⁺	"	200	PO ₄ ³⁻	Sodium	3000
Pd ²⁺	Chloride	20	WO ₄ ²⁻	"	40
Al ³⁺	"	160	CN ⁻	Potassium	400

Numerous new reagents continue to be proposed for the spectrophotometric determination of iron. The authors (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 97) have given a survey of the important reagents proposed for this purpose. *N*-Acetyl-*N*-phenylhydroxylamine is also one of the good reagents. No claim for its superiority over other reagents is made.

The authors express their gratitude to Principal Bhim Sen for providing facilities in the college.